

PESANTREPRENEUR AS THE MOVEMENT OF THE LOCAL COMMUNITY ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRAK

Pesantrenpreneur memiliki potensi besar untuk tidak hanya memperkuat peran pesantren sebagai lembaga pendidikan, tetapi juga sebagai motor pengembangan ekonomi lokal. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengungkap secara detail bagaimana gerakan pesantrenpreneur di Pondok Pesantren Lintang Songo dijadikan sebagai pengembangan perekonomian pesantren dan untuk mengetahui apa saja strategi Pondok Pesantren Lintang Songo dalam menggerakkan eksistensi pesantrenpreneurnya. Penelitian ini adalah penelitian kualitatif dengan pendekatan studi kasus. Pengumpulan data dengan menggunakan observasi, wawancara terstruktur dan dokumentasi, sedangkan teknik analisis data yang digunakan adalah analisa model Miles dan Huberman. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa Pondok Pesantren Lintang Songo telah menjalankan berbagai tahapan berpesantrenpreneur dengan baik, di antaranya: 1) tahapan magang pesantren, 2) tahapan peluncuran pesantren, 3) tahapan tinggal landas pesantren dan 4) tahapan kematangan pesantren. Tidak hanya itu, pesantren ini juga memiliki empat strategi untuk menggerakkan eksistensinya di masyarakat secara luas, di antaranya: 1) berkolaborasi dengan masyarakat setempat untuk mengelola pertanian dan perkebunan, 2) merekrut tenaga bantu dari para santri untuk berbagai produksi pesantren, 3) bekerjasama dengan pemerintah daerah dalam melakukan pendampingan peningkatan skill para santri dalam berpesantrenpreneur dan 4) menyewa lahan masyarakat untuk dijadikan sebagai lahan produktif. Dampak adanya pesantrenpreneur di Pondok Pesantren Lintang Songo ini sangat dirasakan oleh para santri dan masyarakat, terutama dalam pengembangan perekonomian masyarakat lokal.

Kata Kunci: *Pesantrenpreneur, Pondok Pesantren, Perekonomian Masyarakat.*

ABSTRACT

Pesantrenpreneur has great potential to not only strengthen the role of pesantren as an educational institution, but also as a motor for local economic development. This research aims to reveal in detail how pesantrenpreneur movement at the Islamic Boarding School (pesantren) of Lintang Songo is used as a development of pesantren economy and to find out what strategies of Pesantren Lintang Songo has in driving the existence of its pesantrenpreneurs. This research is a qualitative study with a case study approach. Data collection using observation, structured interviews and documentation, while the data analysis technique used is the Miles and Huberman model analysis. The research results indicate that Pesantren Lintang Songo has carried out various stages of pesantrenpreneurship well, including: 1) Pesantren internship stage, 2) Pesantren launch stage, 3) Pesantren take-off stage and 4) Pesantren maturity stage. Not only that, this pesantren also has four strategies to drive its existence in the wider community, including: 1) collaborating with the local community to manage agriculture and plantations, 2) recruiting assistants from students for various pesantren productions, 3) collaborating with the local government in providing assistance to improve the skills of students in pesantren entrepreneurship and 4) renting community land to be used as productive land. The impact of pesantrenpreneurs at Pesantren Lintang Songo is greatly felt by the students and the community, especially in the development of the local community economy.

Keywords: *Pesantrenpreneur, Islamic Boarding School, Community Economy*

INTRODUCTION

Pesantren is an Islamic educational institution that aims to produce complete Muslims and implement Islamic teachings consistently in daily life (Budiyanto & Machali, 2014). Pesantren, as a traditional Islamic educational institution in Indonesia, has long been a center for the formation of character and values for its students (Usman, 2013). However, in recent years, pesantren (Islamic boarding schools) have also begun to become the focus of local economic development through pesantrenpreneurs (Kurniawan, 2022). The term pesantrenpreneur was first introduced by Bank Indonesia at the Indonesia Syaria Economic Festival (ISEF) in 2017 and was later reinforced by a statement from the Indonesian Young Entrepreneurs Association (Himpunan Pengusaha Muda Indonesia/HIPMI) (ISEF, 2022). The concept of pesantrenpreneur aims to transform Islamic boarding schools into new centers of power in the economic moderation movement, so that they can become drivers of economic growth, development and wider distribution of community welfare (Kurniawan, 2022). Historically, Islamic boarding schools have not only played a role as places for religious education, but have also become agents of change and social mobility for society and the nation (Ichsan, 2021). As stated by Sjadzili (2007), pesantren have five key roles in society, including as institutions that encourage devotion and civilization, take part in social and economic change, and develop visions, missions and fulfill the needs of the community (Ryandono, 2018).

This phenomenon is relevant in the context of pesantren throughout Indonesia, including a pesantren Lintang Songo Bantul Yogyakarta. This research was chosen because pesantrenpreneur is a relatively new concept and is developing rapidly in Indonesia (Masruroh, N., & Zahirah, F., 2019). Pesantrenpreneurs have great potential to not only strengthen the role of pesantren as educational institutions, but also as a motor for local economic development. In this context, Pesantren Lintang Songo in Bantul Yogyakarta plays an important role as a case study, because it has successfully implemented pesantrenpreneurs well. Therefore, understanding the strategy and existence of pesantrenpreneurs in this pesantren is important to inspire similar efforts in other places. This research focuses on Pesantren Lintang Songo Bantul Yogyakarta. The researchers will examine in depth how pesantrenpreneur movement in this pesantren is carried out, as well as what strategies are used to drive its existence in the local economy. The main focus of this study will be on the stages of pesantrenpreneurship and the strategies adopted by this pesantren.

The problem in this research is how Pesantren Lintang Songo runs pesantrenpreneur movement and what strategies are used in driving its existence in the local economy. This research will reveal in detail how pesantrenpreneur movement in Pesantren Lintang Songo is run and to analyze the strategies used by this pesantren in driving its existence in the local economy. This research has relevance in two contexts.

Scientifically, this research will provide a good understanding of pesantrenpreneur and the role of pesantren in local economic development. Practically, the findings of this study can provide guidance for other pesantren who want to apply the concept of pesantrenpreneur. This research is expected to provide an important contribution in understanding how pesantrenpreneur can be a motor for local economic and community development, as well as inspire similar efforts in other places. The success of Pesantren Lintang Songo in this case can be an inspiring example for other pesantren who also want to play an active role in driving the local economy while maintaining strong religious values (Ichsan, 2019).

To identify the extent to which this research differs from previous research, the researcher has conducted various literature reviews, including: First, the research of Muhamad Nafik Hadi Ryandono entitled "The Role of Islamic Boarding Schools in Economic Empowerment in East Java in the 20th Century" (Ryandono, 2018). Second, the research by Nikmatul Masruroh and Farah Zahirah entitled "Branding Strategy in the Implementation of Pesantren Preneur" (Masruroh, N., & Zahirah, F., 2019). Third, Zaenal Afandi's research entitled "Entrepreneurship Education Strategy at Al-Mawaddah Islamic Boarding School, Kudus" (Afandi, 2019). Fourth, research by Safika Rosyidatul Arifah entitled "The Role of the Mukmin Mandiri Islamic Boarding School in Overcoming Unemployment Through the Empowerment of Santri" (Arifah, 2020). Fifth, research by Achmad Dudin entitled "Economic Development in Five Islamic Boarding Schools in Lamongan Regency, East Java" (Dudin, 2013). Sixth, Marlina's research entitled "The Potential of Islamic Boarding Schools in the Development of Sharia Economics" (Marlina, 2014). Seventh, Research by A. Sugandi, H.B. Tanjung and RK Rusli entitled "The Role of Modern Islamic Boarding Schools (Ponpes) in Community Economic Empowerment" (A Sugandi, 2017), and the eighth study conducted by Yoyok Rimbawan entitled "Pesantren and Economy: Economic Empowerment at the Darul Falah Bendo Munga Islamic Boarding School; Krian Sidoarjo, East Java" (Rimbawan, 2012). From the eight literature reviews and because no similar themes were found, research on pesantren entrepreneurs and the local community economic development movement at Pesantren Lintang Songo is considered to be important new research and needs to be explained comprehensively to the community.

METHOD

The type of research in this study is qualitative research with a case study approach. Through this case study, researchers intensively conduct scientific, detailed and comprehensive research activities on an event and all activities towards the object being studied (Sugiyono, 2017). The location of this research was carried out at Pondok Pesantren Islamic Studies Center Aswaja Lintang Songo Piyungan Bantul Yogyakarta.

Data collection techniques in this research are as follows: 1) observation, 2) structured interviews and 3) documentation (Creswell, 2015). In order for the data obtained to have a high level of truth and validity, the researcher carried out data validity tests by: 1) extending interaction with informants, 2) conducting more serious observations and 3) testing using triangulation (Moleong, 2018). Meanwhile, the data analysis technique in this study is to use the Miles and Huberman model analysis with the following stages: 1) data reduction, 2) data presentation and 3) drawing conclusions (Sukmadinata, 2013).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Pesantrenpreneur: An Initial Concept

The term pesantrenpreneur is a combination of Pesantren educational institutions and entrepreneurship. In the last few years, pesantrenpreneur has become an attraction because its role has been greatly felt by the wider community. Therefore, the combination of these concepts is a strategic step in giving birth to a generation of the nation that is ready with an entrepreneurial spirit by emphasizing business ethics and moral values of Islamic boarding schools, so that they can be integrated in every

business activity by always adhering to the values of sharia in Islamic economics (Husnurrosyidah, 2019).

To understand pesantrenpreneur, researchers refer to Drayton's concept. Drayton divides the social entrepreneurial cycle into four important stages, namely: First, the Internship Period. This period is a long period because entrepreneurs are in the process of seeking experience, skills and trust for many people in bringing about greater social change. Second, the Launch Period. This period is the beginning of entrepreneurs starting to explore, test and prove the ideas they have had so far (Puspitasari, 2019).

Third, Takeoff Period. This period is also a long period because entrepreneurs will consolidate in their organizations and continue their ideas, so that the ideas spread and are widely accepted in society. Fourth, Maturity Period. This period is the core period where entrepreneurs have provided evidence that the results of their ideas have a real and large impact on society (Puspitasari, 2019).

Pesantrenpreneur developed by Drayton can be understood in the context of pesantren institution. It means that during the internship period, pesantren has a long process of experience in establishing a pesantren based on pesantrenpreneur. During the launch period, pesantren educates students to continue to carry out their entrepreneurial concept, so that the idea can be proven by many groups, especially among the general public. During the take-off period, pesantren also optimizes its entrepreneurial ideas and consolidates that its economic movement can be a solution for the lives of the people around pesantren. Meanwhile, during the maturity period, pesantren has proven and provided evidence of economic solutions that have been conceptualized and implemented so far, so that the existence of its pesantrenpreneur movement can be felt in real terms by various groups.

2. Pesantrenpreneur at Pesantren Lintang Songo as a Solution for Developing the Local Community Economy

To understand pesantrenpreneurs at Pesantren Lintang Songo, researchers refer to the social entrepreneurial cycle through four important stages (Puspitasari, 2019), namely:

a. Pesantren Internship Stage

Pesantren Lintang Songo or commonly known as Lintang Songo has a long history of how this pesantren moves its preaching in improving the economy of the residents of pesantren and the surrounding residents. If we look back into its history, the beginning of the land that was used as agricultural land, plantations, fisheries and forestry owned by pesantren was barren land and far from fertile. When the barren land was irrigated from the Kaliopak River several years ago, the land could be used by pesantren with various entrepreneurship programs based on existing pesantren values (Personal Interview with Kiai HK, 12/08/2023).

At that point, Pesantren Lintang Songo continued to learn to seek experience and skills in the field of environment and entrepreneurship. Through various processes that were carried out, little by little the public's trust began to grow with the hope of being able to provide many social benefits from the existence of pesantren in the community. It is as stated by KH. HK who is the caretaker of pesantren:

“The process of becoming Lintang Songo today was indeed very long, sir. Because our land is barren, what we did was just to change how the barren land of pesantren can be useful for pesantren and the residents. Since long ago, we have hoped that this pesantren would be a different pesantren from the others, both different in

accepting the background of its students, and different in managing the economy for their independence.” (Personal Interview with Kiai HK, 12/08/2023).

The results of the interview indicate that the internship period of pesantren Lintang Songo to become an pesantren entrepreneur requires a long and dynamic process, especially since the community in this pesantren is not a religious community. So it is difficult to gain the trust of the community. However, with strong determination, this internship period has been passed by this pesantren by continuing to improve the quality of the programs that it continues to run.

b. Pesantren Launch Stage

Having a strong determination and experiencing several failures in exploring its entrepreneurship, this Islamic boarding school continues to learn to evaluate everything that has been done. So that from the results, the right solution can be found to carry out a follow-up plan. Various explorations, testing programs and continuing to prove the economic ideas that are run make this Islamic boarding school even better in acting.

The launch period of this pesantren was the initial period of how this pesantren implemented pesantrenpreneur program. As an pesantrenpreneur, this pesantren encourages its students to explore their potential in entrepreneurship independently . Santri (students of pesantren) are given the freedom to cultivate agriculture, fisheries and plantations (Rustam & Ichsan, 2020). Of course, many students experienced failure in the beginning of their entrepreneurship, but that failure actually became a whip for evaluation material in starting entrepreneurship again.

Pesantren has understood the economic problems and is able to identify what parts must be lived through, what parts must be abandoned and what parts must be improved. With this, this period becomes a take-off period which is certainly a better period than the previous period. It is as stated by Ustadz FS, a teacher and chairman of the male management of Pesantren Lintang Songo Bantul, as follows:

“Since starting to seriously work on the land that was originally barren, the community began to be involved. Starting to work on agriculture, plantations and forestry. Agriculture, such as participating in cultivating rice plants. Plantations, such as participating in planting kale, chilies and other vegetables. While forestry, such as participating in caring for teak trees.” (Personal Interview with Ustadz FS, 17/09/2023).

The statement indicates that the launching period has been passed by this pesantren with various involvements of students and the surrounding community in driving its economic independence. This launching period is the starting point for how students and the community better understand how to actualize their potential in strengthening the quality of their economic life in the future.

c. Pesantren Take-Off Stage

After going through the two periods above, another period that Pesantren Lintang Songo must go through is the take-off period. This period is quite a long period in the process of becoming an pesantrenpreneur. During this period, pesantren carries out various consolidations, discussions, internal and external deliberations, creates as many networks as possible and carries out various lobbies in strengthening the program, so that through these various activities, the programs and ideas that have been implemented can be more directly accepted by the wider community. Through discussions and deliberations during this take-off period, this pesantren has implemented various solutions, so that the difficult economy, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, has changed with various programs that are implemented in order to uphold the principle of placing the welfare of the people above all else.

It is proven that since the last 15 years, many agencies and individuals have visited this pesantren to see how pesantrenpreneur can be run in pesantren, even though at that time it was still very simple. The large number of people attending pesantren made pesantren prefer to strengthen its economic quality. It can be proven at that time many economic programs had been implemented, both involving students and surrounding residents as expressed below:

“After being a little known by the community regarding pesantren that upholds the values of independence, we also promote this program through the Bantul Regency DPRD. Through the legislative network, our pesantren is better known in the Regency, so that the economic programs that are run can be seen and realized by many people.” (Personal Interview with Kiai HK, 12/08/2023).

d. Pesantren Maturity Stage

This maturity period has been carried out by Pesantren Lintang Songo with various entrepreneurship programs that are felt by students and the community. The results of the ideas have a real impact and have a big influence on students and the community, as can be seen below:

a. Agriculture Sector

Since the beginning, *Pesantren* Lintang Songo has been working with the community to manage agricultural land. Therefore, there are at least several agricultural fields that are cultivated and enjoyed by the surrounding community, including: 1) planting rice in the rainy season and 2) planting corn in the dry season. It is as stated by one of the teachers as follows:

“Here, since the beginning of planting corn and rice, the community has been involved. Therefore, when the harvest season arrives, they can get the harvest that they have worked on. In fact, some of the land is fully worked by the poor, so that the harvest is also purely for the benefit of the community.” (Personal Interview with Ustadz SA, 12/08/2023).

The expression is interesting if understood in the context of the contribution of pesantrenpreneurs, the subject of entrepreneurship has a strong impact on the social community around it. Not only when the results are obtained, but in the process of getting the economic results, they are actively involved in it.

b. Plantation Sector

In the plantation sector, this pesantren also runs various plantation-based programs that involve the local community, such as planting chilies, tomatoes, kale, eggplants and others. Some of these plantation programs are managed by the students themselves, and others are managed by the community. Those managed by the community include planting chilies and kale. It is as stated by Kiai HR as follows:

“Chili and water spinach plants are fully managed by the surrounding community and 90% of the results are for themselves. For other plants, usually if they need more manpower, they involve the community, such as hoeing, spraying in many areas.” (Personal Interview with Kiai HK, 12/08/2023).

The results of the interview explain that there is community involvement in pesantrenpreneurship of this pesantren. It seems that this pesantren applies discipline seriously to the residents of pesantren, especially to the students. Although some of the students are still of Junior High School age (SMP/MTs), they still get a duty in the garden to manage vegetables every day. Not only that, if the students start to have trouble managing it, pesantren will involve the

community to help manage it. For that, increasing the productivity of santri and the community in the economy continues to be carried out in this pesantren.

c. Fisheries Sector

This pesantren manages the fisheries sector and has more than three fish ponds. There is one pond for cultivating tilapia, one pond for cultivating goldfish and there are two ponds for cultivating catfish. The management of these fish ponds is all handed over to the students. However, the harvest of this fish farming is divided into several parties, namely divided to be cooked by students, for the surrounding community and sold through the network of the Islamic boarding school owned. It is as stated by ustadzah LN as follows:

“Usually the fish harvest in our pesantren is divided into many parts, sir. Some are sold to people we know. Some are shared with neighbors who are close to pesantren and the rest are cooked for the students' daily meals.” (Personal Interview with Ustadzah LN, 12/08/2023)

This pesantrenpreneur in the fisheries sector has also been run by this pesantren. Unlike other sectors, this fishery is purely managed by students, both in terms of fostering, providing daily food, and harvesting. However, the harvest remains for the benefit of the surrounding community.

d. Forestry Sector

This field is rarely managed by students on a daily basis, because the land of pesantren used for forest management is only planted with teak trees. In the context of pesantrenpreneur, it does not directly impact the economic life of the community, but indirectly the surrounding community feels that the forest managed by pesantren has a large role in supporting and absorbing water when heavy rain hits the village. It is as explained by the community around pesantren below:

“The land planted with teak trees is up there on the mountain, sir. So, the students rarely go there. Indeed, we villagers feel the impact, namely that there are rarely floods here. If one of the forests above is often cut down, it is likely that rainwater will enter the village, down here. So, yes, floods again, in fact there was a sudden flash flood before.” (Personal Interview with Mr. KH, 15/08/2023).

If seen from its benefits, this forestry sector is a long-term economic sector. Therefore, pesantren focuses more on short-term economics, so that it can be directly felt by the community. For that reason, this forestry sector seems like it will continue to be run and left alone for dozens of years, so that when the rainy season arrives, the settlements around the teak forests owned by pesantren do not experience flooding, one of the main causes of which is bare forest land. Because Pesantren Lintang Songo area is geographically located under the small mountains (hills) that surround it.

e. Convection Sector

The convection run by Pesantren Lintang Songo is a sewing convection. This field was initially managed by students professionally with direct guidance from professional tailors from the surrounding community. However, with the large number of sewing orders and the lack of students who focus on this field in recent years, the sewing convection is currently mostly managed by the community. It is as expressed by Kiai HR as follows:

“Previously, it was still managed by students, but today there are only a few. It is due to many factors, sir. First, students rarely like to pursue this sewing field. Second, many students who are trained have graduated and left the boarding school, so there is no regeneration. It is our shared homework. Third, the community (as tailors) needs more orders from their work.” (Personal Interview with Kiai HK, 12/08/2023)

If understood from the context of pesantrenpreneur, this pesantren seems to understand that the convection sector has not been fully implemented by the students, because santri in this pesantren are more focused and like other fields. At this point, it is a strength in itself that the empowerment of local communities carried out by pesantren can be proven and have a big impact on the economy of the surrounding community.

f. Industrial Sector

Seriously, this field was only opened in 2021 and the training wave was opened in 2022. The industrial sector of Pesantren Lintang Songo is the existence of the Job Training Center (Balai Latihan Kerja/BLK) from the Indonesian Ministry of Manpower. The BLK chosen at this pesantren is the production of cakes made from local ingredients. After bread, in the future there will be coffee making training. It is as stated by the head of the industrial sector of Pesantren Lintang Songo below:

“For now, BLK pesantren Lintang Songo focuses on cake production. Cake ingredients are taken from local ingredients around pesantren. One of them is making donuts, pizza and so on.” (Personal Interview with Mrs. LRM, 12/08/2023).

From other interview results, it was found that the training participants in this field were mostly intended for the general public. This is proven that until now there have been three waves, the majority of which are from people who do not have permanent jobs, so it is hoped that this training can improve their quality of life through local production in their respective families.

g. Culinary and Other Sectors

This sector has long been run in this pesantren, namely making simple bread for the benefit of various big events. Usually this pesantren makes bread from orders from agencies or entrusted to community stalls, so that the bread that pesantren makes is not wasted and can always be finished.

Another sector that pesantren produces from the results of pesantrenpreneur is making dishwashing soap to be distributed to guests who come and some of it is distributed to the surrounding community. Not infrequently, some stalls also buy soap produced by this pesantren for their needs, such as noodle stalls, chicken noodles, meatballs and the like. One of the customers who has bought products in this field said:

“Dishwashing products here are cheaper, sir. One bottle costs Rp. 4,000. In the stalls, it can be more expensive than that. As a small stall, we prefer the cheap ones with the same quality.” (Personal Interview with Mr. TS, 18/11/2023).

The expression that can be concluded, that pesantrenpreneur carried out by Pesantren Lintang Songo has been proven to provide benefits and contributions not only for the students, but also for the local community. Not only that, as a local product (both bread production and dishwashing soap), this pesantren wants to ease the economic burden of the community around pesantren.

3. Strategy of Pesantren Lintang Songo in Driving the Existence of Pesantrenpreneur

In driving the existence of its pesantrenpreneur, Pesantren Lintang Songo has several strategies that are implemented, including the following:

- a. Collaborate with local communities to manage agriculture, plantations, and sewing convections sector

Pesantren Lintang Songo has established a close partnership with the local community to manage agricultural land, plantations and sewing convections. They plant rice and corn in the appropriate season, with active participation from the community. They also work on various sewing orders from the wider community. This provides an opportunity for underprivileged communities to be involved in the planting process, so that the harvest can be used for their benefit. Plantation programs, such as planting chilies, tomatoes, kale and eggplant, also involve the local community. It also applies to jahiy convections. This collaboration helps create sustainable jobs and economic resources while creating a mutualistic symbiosis, because Pesantren Lintang Songo and the community each benefit from the partnership in managing agriculture sector, plantations and sewing convections.

- b. Recruiting assistants from students for various pesantren productions

Pesantren Lintang Songo also utilizes the santri as human resources for various pesantren productions. Santri (student of pesantren) can be involved in production activities such as managing fish farming, making dish soap and others. It not only helps pesantren in meeting internal needs, but also provides opportunities for santri to develop skills and expertise that can be useful in the business world in the future.

- c. Collaborating with the government in providing assistance to improve the skills of santri in becoming pesantrenpreneur

Pesantren Lintang Songo collaborates with the government to improve students' entrepreneurial skills. This collaboration can include entrepreneurship training, guidance in business management and access to resources that support the development of pesantren businesses. One form of this collaboration is in the industrial sector. This pesantren has a BLK that is supported and facilitated by the Indonesian Ministry of Manpower for the production of various types of cakes processed from local ingredients available at pesantren and the surrounding community. With the support of the government, students can have better access to understand how to improve their skills and abilities to become successful entrepreneurs.

- d. Renting community land to be used as productive land

Pesantren Lintang Songo also uses land rented from the local community as productive land. It can include agricultural land, plantations or other land that can be used for economic activities. By renting the land, pesantren can increase production and create economic opportunities for the local community. The profits from this productive land can be used to support educational programs and pesantrenpreneur activities.

Through these strategies, Pesantren Lintang Songo can drive the existence of its pesantrenpreneurs by collaborating with the community, utilizing the energy of students, getting support from the local government and optimizing productive land. It helps create a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem in pesantren and encourages the development of pesantrenpreneurs in the region.

CONCLUSION

The impact of the existence of pesantrenpreneurs is clearly felt by the students and the community, especially in the development of the local community economy. One of pesantren that consistently provides strengthening of the community's economy is Pesantren Lintang Songo. This pesantren continues to promote various entrepreneurship programs, both among internal students and in the surrounding community with four important stages. These four stages are consistent and professional so that various movements can support the economic growth of pesantren and the surrounding community better. Not only that, there are at least four strategies used by Pesantren Lintang Songo Yogyakarta to increase the economic strength of the community as the existence of the movement, namely first, collaborating with the local community to manage agriculture, plantations and sewing convections. Second, recruiting assistants from the students for various pesantren productions. Third, collaborating with the government in providing assistance to improve the skills of students in becoming pesantrenpreneurs. Fourth, renting community land to be used as productive land.

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